

FORMING A CULTURE OF SPEECH AMONG LEGAL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the formation of a culture of speech among students of legal fields. This scientific study was carried out in several stages. First, the subject of the study was determined, the topic of the article was clearly formulated, and its relevance was substantiated. Further, the purpose and objectives of the study were determined.

A lawyer is a specialist with a higher education in the legal field who is engaged in practical activities. Within its powers, it applies the norms of the current legislation in order to ensure the legality of the actions of individuals or legal entities [4, c.334]. A successful lawyer not only prepares procedural documents, analyzes judicial practice and navigates the law, but also negotiates, communicates with his clients, government and judicial authorities, acts in a variety of communicative roles, so the search for effective methodological ways to improve the level of students' speech culture does not stop, formation of language experience that ensures the effectiveness of communication in various areas of professional activity.

The culture of speech is a broad concept. It includes a set of elements, the purpose of which is to best influence the recipient of information [2, c.12].

Components of cultural speech:

- content;
- an extensive vocabulary;

- observance of lexical norms;
- logical presentation of thought;
- the correct composition of statements;
- clear diction.

Language legal culture is formed, first of all, in the process of mastering the legal language and its direct use in professional legal activities, therefore, in the classroom, students should be involved as much as possible in the process of debatable and analytical communication[3, c.25]. In the process of discussion, the student learns to accurately express his thoughts, actively defend his point of view, argue with reason, and refute the erroneous position of a fellow student. The correctness and literacy of speech have a positive effect on personal self-esteem. The effective development of professional speech is ensured by the creation of a positive motivation for students to develop a culture of speech and is implemented using the methods of introspection, self-assessment, mutual analysis and mutual assessment.

The ability to communicate, conduct a professional dialogue and achieve success in the communication process, using all the richness of the native and foreign languages, are not only universal (general cultural), but also general professional competencies[1, c.39]. A specialist with a higher education must be a priori an intelligent person, i.e., quickly and adequately responding to changes in various situations, widely informed in various fields of science, technology and culture, and able to share his knowledge clearly, logically and reasonably. Qualification requirements for graduates of technical universities imply fluency in a foreign language (in Europe - two European languages), so the teachers of the department of foreign languages introduce effective and efficient methods of teaching students foreign languages. But in order to achieve the set task, teachers are forced to teach students to correctly and clearly express their thoughts in their native language, which, unfortunately, was not formed among the majority of school graduates. In the process of studying native and foreign languages, language, cognitive and communication skills and abilities are improved, which contribute to the achievement of a complex of communicative, general educational and educational goals.

Improving the culture of oral and written speech among law students requires daily preparation. Practice is needed to ensure that speech is correct, clear, precise, understandable, figurative, emotional and expressive. Actively participate in meaningful conversations and conversations; be included in the discussion of problems, issues that arise among friends, colleagues, relatives; often speak at seminars and practical classes. All this

contributes to the development of mental activity, forms speaking skills, develops and improves the culture of speech. Correspondence largely contributes to the development of public speaking skills, the formation of one's own style of speech. The letters should raise not only domestic issues, but also social problems. The ability to evaluate the speech activity of speakers is a training in oratory, eloquence. It is necessary to pay attention not only to the content of the speech of speakers speaking at meetings, lectures, on radio and television, but also to attach great importance to the presentation of material, speech skills, oratory techniques.

Every day a lawyer deals with a variety of life phenomena, which, in turn, he must be able to correctly evaluate, make the right decision in accordance with them, and, if necessary, convince him of the correctness of his point of view. Since a lawyer is a public profession, it is common for a lawyer to encounter representatives of different social groups, professions and people with different levels of culture and education. And in each case, the lawyer must choose the right words, the right tone, the right arguments. In other words, a lawyer must be able to find an approach to every person who addresses him. If a lawyer violates linguistic norms, for example, uses jargon, dialectisms and vernacular in his speech, then this may lead to adverse consequences: a negative reaction from the public, distrust of listeners, lack of respect, the appearance of doubts in his general and professional knowledge. It is important that "communication in the legal sphere meets the requirements of legal culture, one of the components of which legal scholars consider the culture of speech." The prestige of law enforcement agencies,

justice authorities and the profession as a whole directly depends on the level of speech culture of each lawyer. Most lawyers lecture on legal topics, act in court as a defender, prosecutor or representative, and for this it is necessary to have public speaking skills, which once again proves the important role of speech culture in legal activities.

A lawyer in his practice has to deal with people of a wide variety of professions and different levels of culture. And in each case, it is necessary to find the right tone, words, arguing and competently expressing thoughts. The content of their explanations and testimonies depends on how accurately these persons understand the speech of a lawyer. The ability to speak in public, language proficiency has long been considered a necessary professional quality of a lawyer. A lawyer acts in various communicative roles and his violation of language norms can cause a negative reaction from his interlocutors. The high rating of many modern lawyers is determined by the impression of general culture and intelligence that their speeches leave, their impeccable command of the literary language, the ability to accurately, clearly, correctly and logically express an idea. This is a prerequisite for the successful self-presentation of a judicial speaker. This means that language is a tool with which all thoughts are formed and transmitted, it is a professional weapon of a lawyer. And questions of the culture of a lawyer's speech are raised by life itself, by practical necessity.

For the formation of a speech culture of a student of a legal direction, the following exercises are advisable:

- retelling of the text;

- solving tests without answer options;
- selection of synonyms for various words.

The main criterion for the culture of speech is normativity, which includes accuracy and clarity, correctness, purity of speech, i.e. the absence in it of dialect, colloquial words, narrowly professional expressions, inappropriately used foreign words. In addition, speech is considered cultural, which is characterized by speech skill: logical harmony, rich vocabulary, variety of grammatical structures, artistic expressiveness. Every day a lawyer deals with the most diverse phenomena of civil and professional life. They need to be deeply and correctly known, assessed, make the right decisions, convince others of the correctness of their point of view. Therefore, his general culture should be consistent with professional culture. Violation of language norms by a lawyer can cause a negative reaction from interlocutors. In addition, each lawyer, giving lectures and making reports, acts as a speaker, as a propagandist of legal knowledge. Prosecutors and lawyers make public speeches every day in court cases, so they need to have public speaking skills.

Insufficient attention to the general problems of the native language and the language of jurisprudence on the part of lawyers leads to a decrease in the quality of judicial speech and other speeches, and the incomprehensibility of written texts. This testifies to the unwillingness of the speaker-lawyer to think about the meaning of the words used, about his disrespect for the language. After all, the high rating of many lawyers is determined by the impression of a general culture and intelligence that their speeches leave, an impeccable command of

the literary language, the ability to accurately, clearly, correctly and logically express an idea. All these factors are a prerequisite for successful self-presentation, for example, as a court speaker. So, language is a professional means of a lawyer. And questions of the culture of a lawyer's speech are raised by life itself, by practical necessity.

The peculiarity of the speech of a lawyer lies in the richness of professional terminology. Often this makes it difficult to contact an interlocutor from a non-professional environment, which requires the ability to explain legal concepts and terms, definitions, using various techniques and explanations and explanations. The oral speech of lawyers is characterized by a variety of styles. For example, when discussing the problems of lawmaking, legal examination of bills, a scientific style of speech can be used. When the accuser speaks in court, an official business style of speech is used.

The lawyer's speech is defensive in nature and can be delivered in an official business, journalistic style, or a combination of both. An important feature of legal speech is the high responsibility of the author of the speech for his words. Thus, legal errors, non-objective assessments can affect not only human destiny, but also a judicial decision, a different procedural decision. The foundation of legal speech is a deep study of the circumstances of the case, their impeccable legal assessment. Speaking well in court means carefully analyzing the materials of the case, relying on the norms of law, speaking objectively, intelligibly, convincingly, logically, based on the norms of the literary language.

The meaning of the sentence also determines the use of the combinations

"Bring into line" and "in accordance with". It is possible to "make the document conform to the requirements of the official style of speech", but "make the document comply with the requirements of the official style of speech".

Another example is the incorrect use of prepositions. So, the preposition "due to" is often confused with a noun with the preposition "in consequence" / "in consequence". The preposition "due to" is written together, with the letter "e" at the end; means a causal relationship. And the sentences "Due to insufficient evidence" or "New testimonies of witnesses were added as a result" have a different meaning, in this context we are talking about the noun "investigation" and the preposition "with".

A common mistake is the violation of orthoepic norms. Orthoepic norms are "a set of codified rules and norms of oral speech that ensure its compliance with the grammatical bases of the language, which, in turn, systematize the sound design of speech in accordance with the norms that have historically been entrenched in the modern literary language." So, in the context of criminal law, it is relevant to give an example of "convicted" instead of the correct pronunciation of "convicted". Mistakes are "providing", "petition", "inform", "contract", "expert" and many others. It is also necessary to talk about the culture of speech of a lawyer because the legal language is specific. It contains many terms that have a special legal meaning, for example: code, smuggling, alibi, motives for a crime, preventive measure, confiscation, etc. Some colloquial words are used as terms, such as: squandering, begging, slander; obsolete: deed, concealment; verbal nouns that are not typical for general use: delivery, failure to report, search. Most

polysemantic words denote special legal concepts. So, the drive is the forced delivery of someone to the investigation and court authorities; to persuade - to force to commit a crime; redemption - termination of a criminal record; an episode is a part of criminal acts, etc. Therefore, in the language of law there are phrases that are not used outside the legal sphere of communication, for example: organizer of a crime, apply measures, commit a crime, immoral act, etc.

This is the most difficult and most interesting of all professional languages.

Thus, the competent speech of a lawyer plays an important role in his professional activity. The culture of speech of a lawyer is important for the ability to negotiate, advise citizens, speak in public, logically and reasonably express one's thoughts. The prestige of law enforcement agencies, the judiciary and the profession as a whole directly depends on the level of speech culture of each lawyer.

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